

**CRITICAL HURDLES AND INFLUENCES IN NETWORKS (CHAIN):
A QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS ON THE DETERMINANTS AND
IMPACTS OF THE MARKETING CHAIN ON BANANA
PRODUCTION IN PALIMBANG**

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Critical Hurdles and Influences in Networks (CHAIN): A Quantitative Analysis on the Determinants and Impacts of the Marketing Chain on Banana Production in Palimbang

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Abstract

This study investigated the factors that influenced the banana marketing chain and their impact on market dynamics in Palimbang as the banana market in Palimbang was a crucial agricultural product. In the Philippines, the banana industry played a vital role in local economies, with the country ranking third globally in banana production. Despite its significance, various challenges, including marketing bottlenecks, hindered profitability and fair pricing for consumers. These bottlenecks often resulted in reduced income for farmers and limited access to markets. Utilizing a quantitative approach, data was collected from 52 survey participants using random sampling technique. The findings indicated that the interconnection between marketing and production significantly affected farm outputs, often leading to stagnation or decline. This marketing constraint was crucial for enhancing profitability and ensuring affordable banana prices for rural consumers. The study revealed that the majority of the participants were well-informed about the banana marketing chain and its determinants, regardless of the scale of production. The consensus was that these factors greatly influenced the market flow in Palimbang. Hence, the agro-industry marketing chain for bananas in Palimbang played a critical role in the community's economy, with marketing constraints being a key element in securing better returns and fair pricing for consumers. By improving the supply chain and ensuring fair pricing mechanisms, the lives of farmers could have been enhanced significantly. Moreover, boosting the banana industry would have had a positive ripple effect on the overall economy of Palimbang, making it an essential area for development and investment.

Keywords: *agriculture, agro-industry, banana marketing chain, quantitative analysis, supply chain*

Introduction

Southeast Asia historically played a pivotal role in the origins of both plantains and bananas. The introduction of bananas to the Americas is credited to the Spanish and Portuguese during the 16th century. Similarly, they were brought to Spain's Canary Islands and Hispaniola (modern-day Dominican Republic and Haiti) during the 15th century. Additionally, it is believed that bananas were first introduced to Africa around 200 B.C. and to the Americas as far back as the Paleolithic era. Over the last century, the global banana trade has expanded rapidly. Approximately 15 years ago, bananas were second only to citrus fruits in terms of market value on the global fruit trade (Shrestha et al., 2018).

Today, bananas are one of the most widely cultivated crops globally, with over 150 countries producing an estimated 105 million metric tons annually. By the late 19th century, technological advancements such as railroads and refrigerated ocean transport enabled the international trade of bananas, solidifying their status as the most traded fruit in the world. By 2016, the global export value of bananas reached approximately \$8 billion, with a retail value between \$20 and \$25 billion. Bananas are among the most popular and affordable fruits worldwide. In tropical regions, such as parts of Africa, Latin America, the Caribbean, and the Pacific, bananas are cultivated alongside other tropical fruits like pineapples. However, Latin America dominates banana exports, supplying fruit to markets in Europe, North America, Russia, and China, contributing significantly to the economies of exporting nations (BananaLink, 2023).

In the Philippines, bananas are the most important fruit crop, with the sector involving farmers, cooperatives, merchants, exporters, and manufacturers. Despite this, large multinational corporations largely control the industry. The country produces three main varieties of bananas: Cavendish, which constitutes 50% of the total banana production; Lakatan, accounting for 11%; and Saba, a significant cooking variety, comprising 29%. Globally, the Philippines rank third in banana production after China and India (FAOStat, 2017). With that, this study aims to identify the key factors influencing the banana marketing chain and assess their impact on market dynamics. Additionally, it explores the current state of banana production in the municipality of Palimbang, evaluating its potential as a key agro-industry. With the banana industry expanding its reach beyond Mindanao to global markets, this research underscores the importance of focusing on banana production as a critical economic driver, considering the widespread consumption of bananas worldwide.

Research Questions

To address the underlying problems concerning the determinants and impacts of the marketing chain on banana production in Palimbang, the study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the banana farmers in terms of:
 - 1.1. length in farming;
 - 1.2. areas of yield farming;

- 1.3. tenure status; and
- 1.4. banana variety.
2. What are the marketing chains of banana production in Palimbang?
3. What are the extent effects of determinants to the banana market chain of Palimbang?

Literature Review

Banana production in the Philippines has seen significant growth, particularly with the Cavendish variety, which dominates export markets. According to Nozawa (2012), the total production of Cavendish bananas increased from 4.6 million metric tons in 2010, reflecting a substantial rise in both yield and area harvested over the years. This growth can be attributed to improved agricultural practices and investments in technology that enhance productivity. The establishment of cooperatives has also played a vital role in supporting smallholder farmers by providing access to resources and markets (Nozawa, 2012). In Palimbang specifically, MAM Agri Venture Industrial Corp. has initiated a significant investment to develop a 250-hectare banana plantation, which is expected to generate approximately 350 local jobs (MindaNews, 2021). This venture not only aims to boost local production but also seeks to integrate local farmers into the supply chain through partnerships with larger firms like Unifrutti Tropical Philippines. Such collaborations can enhance knowledge transfer regarding best practices in banana cultivation and post-harvest handling.

Quality assurance is paramount in the banana industry due to the highly perishable nature of the fruit and its global market demands. The need for rigorous standards is underscored by the requirement for compliance with both local regulations and international export standards (Nozawa, 2012). Strict pest and disease control measures are essential to maintain quality throughout the production process (Nozawa, 2012). Furthermore, effective infrastructure for packing and transporting bananas is critical to ensure that they meet freshness requirements upon reaching consumers. The integration of quality standards into production practices can significantly affect market access. For instance, studies have shown that producers who adhere to stringent quality protocols are more likely to secure contracts with exporters and retailers (Santoso et al., 2022). The establishment of clear quality benchmarks not only benefits producers by enhancing their marketability but also assures consumers of product safety and reliability.

The study conducted by Santoso et al. (2022) on banana trading chains in Jayapura emphasized that different trading channels exhibit varying levels of efficiency. Their findings suggest that shorter supply chains tend to be more efficient due to lower transportation costs and reduced handling times. Thus, fostering an open distribution network that minimizes intermediaries can significantly enhance profitability for local producers. Distribution channels play a crucial role in determining how effectively bananas reach consumers. An open distribution system allows for multiple pathways through which products can be marketed, increasing accessibility for both producers and consumers. Research indicates that efficient distribution channels can reduce costs and improve profit margins for farmers (Santoso et al., 2022). In Palimbang, improvements in local infrastructure have been highlighted as necessary for enhancing distribution efficiency (MindaNews, 2021).

The research conducted along the Hetauda-Dumkibas road corridor in Nepal highlights the importance of institutional frameworks that support supply chain integration (Khadka et al., 2021). By strengthening local institutions that provide extension services, training programs, and market information, stakeholders can enhance their collective efficiency and responsiveness to market demands. The supply chain for an agricultural product includes all the economic activities carried out between those phases, such as the process, delivery, retailing, and wholesaling. It begins with the manufacturing of raw materials for essential commodities and finishes with the consumer's consumption of the final product. These concerns are crucial for developing the agricultural supply chain's overall sustainability (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, FAO, 2014). Value chains serve as the fundamental foundation for comprehending how services and inputs are combined before being used to the development, production, and transformation of a product. It is beneficial to comprehend how the product is physically transferred from the manufacturer to the consumer and how its value rises during this process (Kaplinsky & Morris, 2000).

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized quantitative research methods, employing a descriptive research design to address the problem and achieve the study's objectives. As defined by Creswell (2014), quantitative research is a means for testing objective theories by examining the relationships among variables. These variables are typically measured using instruments that generate numerical data, which can then be analyzed through statistical procedures. Quantitative research may also involve approaches such as survey research and experimental research.

Respondents

This study involved fifty two (52) banana farmers from the municipality of Palimbang, Sultan Kudarat, the participants were selected through simple random sampling technique. This method ensured that every individual in the larger population had an equal chance of being included in the study (Thomas, 2022). The farmers were chosen because their expertise and experience in the banana market in Palimbang were expected to provide valuable insights and contribute significantly to the objectives of the study.

Data Analysis

To effectively structure the study's methodology, the researchers utilized a five-point Likert scale to assess the marketing chain of banana production and its contributing factors. This method offered a systematic framework for examining the dynamics of the banana market. Each stage of the chain, from production to distribution, was carefully analyzed, along with the influence of various factors on the overall process, and to describe the key characteristics of the data collected in this study, statistical tools such as Frequency Distribution, Percentage, and Mean were employed for data analysis. The average weighted mean, or grand mean, was calculated and interpreted using a table of mean scale values.

Table 1. Interpretation and Verbal Descriptions of the Data

Rating	Verbal Description	Interpretation
5	Strongly Agree	Means that you are very much in favor of it at about 9 out of 10 in range of 1-10 or about 80-100%
4	Agree	Means that you are much in favor of it at about of 7-8 in a range of 1-10 or about 61-80%
3	Neutral	Means that you are in favor of it at about of 5-6 in a range of 1-10 or about 41-60%
2	Disagree	Means that you are in favor of it at about of 3-4 in a range of 1-10 Or about 21-40%
1	Strongly Disagree	Means that you are much in favor of it at about of 1-2 in a range of 1-10 or about 1-20%

The level of consensus among the participants regarding the depictions of the banana production market chain and associated factors was ascertained using the calculated average. This method allowed for a quantifiable measure of agreement. The outcome, which was detailed below, had been determined as follow:

Table 2. Level of the Agreement of the Participants

Scale	Range	Verbal Description
5	4.51 – 5.0	Strongly Agree
4	3.51 – 4.50	Agree
3	2.51 – 3.50	Neutral
2	1.51 – 2.50	Disagree
1	0.50 – 1.50	Strongly Disagree

Ethical Considerations

In conducting this study, ethical considerations were paramount to ensure the integrity and respect of all participants involved. Informed consent was obtained from participants prior to data collection, ensuring they were fully aware of the study's purpose, their involvement, and their right to withdraw at any time without consequence. This transparency was crucial for fostering trust and voluntary participation. Confidentiality was strictly maintained by removing personal identifiers from data sets, thereby protecting the privacy of the farmers and encouraging honest responses. The research design also prioritized minimizing potential harm to participants by focusing on their experiences and insights regarding the marketing chain, empowering them with a voice in discussing industry challenges. Furthermore, ethical approval was secured from Sultan Kudarat State University in order to proceed with the conduct of the study, ensuring adherence to established ethical standards for research involving human subjects. As a whole, these considerations aimed to uphold the rights and dignity of all individuals involved while enhancing the study's validity and reliability.

Results and Discussion

This section outlines the findings from the survey questionnaires completed by participants.

Socio-Demographic Profile of the Banana Farmers

Table 3. Frequency and Percentage Distribution in terms of Length in Farming

Length In Farming	Frequency	Percentage
1-5 Years	40	76.92
6-10 Years	7	13.46
11 And Above	5	9.62
Total	N=52	100

The table indicated that a significant majority of the participants, specifically 76.92% (40 individuals), had been engaged in farming for a duration of 1 to 5 years. A smaller group, comprising 13.46% (7 participants), reported having 6 to 10 years of farming experience, while 9.62% (5 participants) had substantial farming tenures of 11 years or more. This data provides a historical overview of the participants' engagement in the farming sector, highlighting the varying levels of experience among them.

The diverse range of farming experience among participants may have considerable implications for the dynamics of the banana marketing chain in Palimbang. Those with shorter farming tenures may exhibit a greater openness to adopting innovative farming practices and technologies, potentially leading to enhanced productivity and efficiency. Conversely, participants with longer tenures might be more inclined to rely on traditional agricultural methods, which could influence their adaptability to market changes and new

agricultural trends. This interplay between tradition and innovation is crucial, as it can significantly shape the overall efficiency and sustainability of the banana marketing chain in the region (Rogers, 2003).

Table 4. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution in terms of Areas of Yield Farming*

<i>Areas Of Yield Farming</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Less One Hectare	16	30.77
1-2 Hectares	25	48.08
3-4 Hectares	7	13.46
5 And Above Hectares	4	7.69
Total	N=52	100

Table 4 revealed that a substantial majority of the participants, specifically 48.08% (25 individuals), were farming on areas ranging from 1 to 2 hectares. This moderate land size likely enabled them to cultivate a significant quantity of bananas, thereby contributing meaningfully to the overall supply within the banana marketing chain. In contrast, 30.77% (16 participants) operated on less than one hectare of land. Despite the smaller size of their farms, these participants may have focused on enhancing the quality of their produce or adopted intensive farming techniques to maximize yield per unit area. On the other hand, 13.46% (7 participants) managed larger farms ranging from 3 to 4 hectares, while 7.69% (4 participants) farmed on areas of 5 hectares or more. These individuals, with their extensive farming operations, likely played a significant role in bolstering the banana supply in Palimbang. Their larger-scale operations could influence various aspects of the banana marketing chain, including pricing strategies and distribution logistics.

This data underscores that the size of the farming area is a critical factor in the dynamics of the banana marketing chain in Palimbang. It not only affects the quantity of banana yield but also shapes the farming practices employed by producers. Larger farms may benefit from economies of scale, allowing for more efficient production and distribution processes (Kassam, 2003). Conversely, smaller farms may adopt niche strategies focusing on high-quality outputs or specialty markets. The diversity in farming scale introduces complexity into the banana marketing chain, creating a dynamic and multifaceted system. This variation can lead to differing impacts on market supply, pricing structures, and consumer preferences, ultimately shaping the overall sustainability and resilience of the agricultural sector in Palimbang (FAO, 2014).

Table 5. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution in terms of Tenure Status*

<i>Tenure Status</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Owner	30	57.69
Tenants	12	23.08
Others	10	19.23
Total	N=52	100

The land tenure status of the farmers has emerged as a significant factor influencing the banana marketing chain in Palimbang. It could determine the scale of banana production, the farming practices employed, and the flow of bananas from the farm to the market. This diversity in land tenure arrangements adds another layer of complexity to the banana marketing chain, making it a dynamic and multifaceted system. Table 5 indicates that a majority of the participants, specifically 57.69% (30 individuals), owned the land they were cultivating. This group, having full control and rights over their land, likely had the freedom to make decisions regarding the cultivation and marketing of bananas. Their ownership status could influence their farming practices, productivity, and overall role in the banana marketing chain. Research shows that land ownership often correlates with increased investment in agricultural improvements and better access to resources (Transportify, 2021).

Furthermore, 23.08% (12 respondents) were tenants of the land they farmed. As tenants, they might be subject to certain restrictions or conditions set by landowners, which could impact their farming methods, scale of operations, and contributions to the banana marketing chain. Tenants may face challenges such as limited access to capital for investment in better farming practices or technologies due to their lack of ownership (FAO, 2024). This situation can lead to a reliance on traditional farming methods or lower productivity levels compared to owner-operators. Additionally, 19.23% (10 participants) selected 'others' as their tenure status. This group may include individuals involved in cooperative farming groups, those farming on communal lands, or those with unique tenure arrangements. The role of cooperatives can be particularly significant in enhancing productivity and market access for smallholders by pooling resources and sharing knowledge (Nozawa, 2016). Such arrangements can also mitigate some disadvantages faced by tenants by providing support systems that facilitate better farming practices.

In the Philippines there are various types of grown variety of bananas, with the Cavendish variety being the most cultivated nationwide, accounting for 53% of the country's total banana production (BananaLink, 2023). However, in the three barangays of Palimbang—Akol, Poblacion, and Badiango—the situation is notably different. The Cardava variety emerges as the most popular among local farmers, with 71.15% (37 out of 52 participants) cultivating it. This variety is recognized for its resistance to pests and diseases, which may make it a preferred choice due to its higher yield potential and market demand. Despite Cavendish being the leading variety in national production, it ranks as the second most popular in these barangays, cultivated by 17.31% of the participants. In contrast, the

Lakatan and Latundan varieties are each grown by 5.77% of participants, making them the least popular choices. These varieties are typically favored for local consumption because of their sweet taste.

Table 6. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution in terms of Banana Variety*

<i>Banana Variety</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Cardava	37	71.15
Cavendish	9	17.31
Lakatan	3	5.77
Latundan	3	5.77
Others	0	0
Total	N=52	100

The choice of banana variety cultivated by farmers in Palimbang is influenced by several factors, including market demand, yield potential, and resistance to pests and diseases. Understanding these factors is crucial for grasping the dynamics of the banana marketing chain in Palimbang. As noted by Lodovice and Lee (2024), different banana varieties can lead to varied market responses and price dynamics within the domestic market. This variability highlights the need for stakeholders in the banana supply chain to develop tailored strategies based on specific varieties to improve market efficiency.

Moreover, recent reports emphasize that while Cavendish bananas dominate export markets due to their global demand, local preferences for varieties like Cardava and Lakatan reflect a significant aspect of consumer behavior that must be considered in marketing strategies (FAO, 2024). The Philippine banana industry continues to face challenges such as pest outbreaks and competition from cheaper imports, which can affect production decisions at the local level (World Bank, 2023). Understanding this interplay between variety choice and market dynamics is essential for enhancing productivity and sustainability within Palimbang's banana marketing chain.

Market Chain Accessibility in Banana Production

Table 7. *Mean Distribution of the Participants in terms of Banana Production and Harvesting*

<i>Banana Production and Harvesting</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
The availability of high-quality planting materials positively influences the banana marketing chain in Palimbang.	4.038	Agree
Adequate farm management practices, such as pest and disease control, contribute to better banana quality and marketability.	3.69	Agree
The adoption of sustainable and environmentally friendly farming practices enhances the banana marketing chain.	3.94	Agree
Proper harvesting techniques, such as harvesting at the right stage of maturity, positively impact banana quality and market value.	3.79	Agree
Grand Mean	3.86	Agree

Table 7 shows the perspectives of the participants on banana production and harvesting, particularly the influence of the banana marketing chain. Participants agreed that the availability of high-quality planting materials plays a vital role in the success of the banana market chain. This underscores the importance of ensuring sufficient supply and accessibility of these materials for production. Additionally, the participants highlighted that effective market chain operations must align with proper farm management practices to produce high-quality and marketable bananas. Farmers also concurred that sustainable farming practices significantly enhance the efficiency and resilience of the banana marketing chain.

The success of banana farming is intricately tied to the use of disease-free, high-quality planting materials. Techniques such as micro propagation and robust seedling sanitation are critical in maintaining crop health and productivity. These methods enable large-scale seedling production while mitigating risks associated with pests and diseases (Tenkouano et al., 2006). The adoption of Good Agricultural Practices (GAP) further supports sustainability in banana farming by minimizing environmental impacts and ensuring that post-harvest processes, including packaging and transportation, produce high-quality and safe bananas (FAO, 2024).

Other research also suggests that transitioning to sustainable agricultural practices in banana farming is influenced by various socioeconomic and psychosocial factors. These practices not only improve farmers' ability to adapt to environmental changes but also enhance the sustainability of production over the long term (Waseem et al., 2020). Evaluating the sustainability of the banana value chain through economic, social, and environmental indicators can identify opportunities for improvement, thereby bolstering its overall effectiveness and sustainability (Gebre & Rik, 2016).

Table 8 presents the results of the data gathered on post-harvest handling and packaging in banana production, which plays a vital role in supporting the overall production chain. The tabulated data, including the mean and grand mean scores, indicate that participants collectively agreed that effective production and harvesting practices are crucial components of the banana marketing chain. With an average rating of 3.79, participants affirmed that proper handling and transportation practices are key to maintaining the quality and freshness of bananas, thereby serving as significant contributors to the market chain. Other factors, such as post-harvest treatments,

adequate labeling, and the availability of storage and cooling facilities, were also rated positively by the participants.

Table 8. Mean Distribution of the Participants in terms of Post Harvesting Handling and Packaging

Post Harvesting Handling and packaging	Mean	Interpretation
I believed that production and harvesting practices play a crucial role in the banana marketing chain in Palimbang.	3.84	Agree
Proper handling and transportation practices help maintain the quality and freshness of bananas during the marketing chain.	3.79	Agree
The use of appropriate post-harvest treatments, such as washing and sanitizing, positively influences banana quality.	3.86	Agree
Adequate packaging and labeling of bananas contribution to their marketability and consumer appeal.	3.94	Agree
The availability of proper storage and cooling facilities ensures longer shelf life and better quality of bananas.	3.71	Agree
Grand Mean	3.83	Agree

These findings align with research by Guo et al. (2020) and Bhanusree et al. (2022), which emphasize the importance of post-harvest practices in preserving banana quality and ensuring success in the market. Guo et al. (2020) explored the role of mechanization and technology in banana post-harvest operations, highlighting that harvesting and transportation remain labor-intensive and costly. Their study suggested that introducing mechanized and automated systems could enhance both quality and marketability. Similarly, Bhanusree et al. (2022) examined the impact of various post-harvest packaging materials on the shelf life and quality of bananas. Their research demonstrated that techniques such as KMnO₄ treatment and wax coating, when combined with suitable packaging strategies, effectively extended the shelf life and preserved the quality of bananas. These measures not only improved the fruit's freshness but also strengthened its contribution to the overall marketing chain.

Table 9. Mean Distribution of the Participants in terms of Market Access and Distribution

Market Access and Distribution	Mean	Interpretation
Access to reliable markets and buyers is important for the successful marketing of bananas in Palimbang.	3.73	Agree
Efficient transportation and logistics systems contribute to the timely delivery of bananas to markets.	3.46	Neutral
The availability of market information and price transparency helps farmers make informed decisions in the banana marketing chain.	3.57	Agree
The establishment of strong market linkages and partnerships positively affects the marketing of bananas.	3.56	Agree
Grand Mean	3.64	Agree

Market access and distribution generally refer to the ability of farmers or retailers to secure favorable pricing terms for consumers. Even with efficient banana production practices, consumers often face higher costs if market access is inadequate. Table 9 highlights a positive outcome based on the data from 52 participants, with the grand mean indicating an overall agreement. In support, Adoye et al. (2023) emphasize the importance of effective post-harvest handling and packaging in maintaining the quality and marketability of bananas. They argue that even with efficient production practices, inadequate market access can result in higher consumer prices. To address this issue, the authors suggest that enhancing market linkages and partnerships is crucial for improving the distribution of banana products. This aligns with broader findings that highlight the significance of reliable markets and transparent pricing information in ensuring fair pricing for consumers and producers alike.

Most participants agreed that post-harvest handling and packaging practices play a crucial role in strengthening the banana marketing chain. They emphasized the importance of reliable markets and buyers, transparent pricing information, and robust market linkages and partnerships in enhancing market accessibility and the distribution of banana products in Palimbang. However, efficient transportation and logistics systems received a mean score of 3.46, interpreted as Neutral. This suggests that participants were divided in their views on the impact of transportation and logistics efficiency on banana production.

In connection, Lucas (2021) discusses the role of transportation and logistics in the banana supply chain. The study found that while some participants rated transportation efficiency as neutral, it remains a critical factor influencing market access. This mixed perception about logistics efficiency echoes the results indicating that improvements in this area could enhance overall banana production and distribution effectiveness. Furthermore, a recent article by Merumba et al. (2022) explores how socioeconomic factors influence market access for smallholder banana farmers, highlighting that reliable market access is crucial for ensuring fair pricing and reducing costs for consumers. This aligns with observations that respondents emphasized the need for robust market linkages to improve accessibility.

Table 10 presented the participants' perceptions regarding quality assurance and standards in banana production in Palimbang. The statement "I believe that market access and distribution play a crucial role in the banana marketing chain in Palimbang" received a mean score of 3.94, indicating agreement among respondents. Similarly, the statement concerning compliance with quality standards and certifications was also agreed upon, with a mean of 3.81. However, the statement "Adequate control measures at different stages

of the marketing chain contribute to consistent banana quality" garnered a neutral interpretation, reflecting mixed opinions among respondents. In contrast, consumer trust and confidence in the quality and safety of bananas received favorable responses, with a mean score of 3.94. The adoption of traceability systems and Good Agricultural Practices (GAP) was rated even higher, achieving a mean score of 4.17. This suggests that respondents recognize the importance of these practices in enhancing consumer confidence and ensuring high-quality banana production.

Table 10. *Mean Distribution of the Participants in terms of Quality Assurance and Standards*

<i>Quality Assurance and Standards</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Compliance with quality standards and certifications enhances the marketability and competitiveness of bananas.	3.81	Agree
Adequate control measures at different stages of the marketing chain contribute to consistent banana quality.	3.35	Neutral
Consumer trust and confidence in the quality and safety of bananas are important determinant of successful marketing.	3.94	Agree
The adoption of traceability systems and good agriculture practices improves the overall quality of bananas.	4.17	Agree
Grand Mean	3.84	Agree

Recent studies support these findings by highlighting the significance of market access and quality assurance in the banana industry. For example, research by Voora et al. (2023) emphasizes that effective market linkages and compliance with quality standards are crucial for maintaining consumer trust and ensuring competitive pricing in global markets. Additionally, studies indicate that implementing GAP can significantly improve product safety and quality while enhancing market access for farmers (FAO, 2022). These insights align with the perceptions expressed by respondents in Palimbang, underscoring the importance of robust market mechanisms and adherence to quality standards in fostering a successful banana marketing chain.

Table 11. *Mean Distribution of the Participants in terms of Marketing Support and Promotion*

<i>Marketing support and Promotion</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Access to market information, training, and technical support helps farmers improve their marketing practices.	3.86	Agree
Effective marketing strategies, such as branding and product differentiation, contribute to successful banana marketing.	4.02	Agree
The availability of financial assistance and credit facilities supports farmer in their marketing activities.	4.17	Agree
Collaboration and networking among farmers and stakeholders strengthen the banana marketing chain.	3.92	Agree
I believe that marketing support and promotion are vital for the successful marketing of bananas in Palimbang.	3.92	Agree
Grand Mean	3.99	Agree

Table 11 reveals that participants provided positive feedback regarding marketing support and promotion, with a grand mean of 3.99, interpreted as "Agree." All statements within this category received mean scores ranging from 3.86 to 4.17, reflecting a shared acknowledgment of the significance of various marketing aspects in the banana value chain. Respondents agreed that maintaining quality assurance and adhering to standards are essential for the success of banana marketing. They also recognized the value of access to market information, training, and technical support in enhancing farmers' marketing practices.

Additionally, effective marketing strategies, such as branding and product differentiation, were acknowledged as key contributors to successful banana marketing. Respondents emphasized the importance of financial assistance and credit facilities in supporting farmers' marketing efforts. Collaboration and networking among farmers and stakeholders were also highlighted as vital for strengthening the banana marketing chain. The grand mean underscores the conclusion that marketing support and promotion are critical factors in the success of the banana marketing chain. These findings highlight the role of consumer awareness in ensuring that bananas are recognized as a significant component of Palimbang's agroindustry. Furthermore, the results emphasize the essential relationship between producers and consumers, which is vital for sustaining and advancing the banana marketing chain.

Impact of Determinants on the Banana Marketing Chain

Table 12. *Mean Distribution of the Participants on the Impact of Banana Production and Harvesting*

<i>Banana Production and Harvesting</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Adequate amount of supply over demand is met accordingly.	4.33	Agree
Ensure that the banana delivered in the market place and area of distribution is in good quality.	3.94	Agree
Environmental protection through sustainable farming will facilitate a good harvest in the future.	4.23	Agree
Grand Mean	4.17	Agree

Table 12 illustrates the extent of the effects of banana production and harvesting on the banana marketing chain, with a grand mean score of 4.17, indicating an overall agreement among participants. Specifically, the statements "Adequate supply meets demand,"

"Bananas delivered to the market are of good quality," and "Environmental protection through sustainable farming will facilitate future harvests" received mean scores of 4.33, 3.94, and 4.23, respectively, all interpreted as agreements. These results are consistent with those presented in Table 7, which had a grand mean of 3.86 and was also interpreted as an agreement. This alignment validates the participants' responses regarding the determinants affecting the banana marketing chain, particularly focusing on production and harvesting.

Based on this data, the researchers are confident that banana production and harvesting, along with their associated parameters, effectively serve as determinants within the banana marketing chain in Palimbang. Recent studies support these findings by emphasizing the importance of sustainable practices and market dynamics in enhancing banana production. For instance, Jamaldin (2024) highlights how market access significantly influences the livelihoods of smallholder farmers in Tanzania, suggesting that improved access can lead to better economic outcomes. Similarly, Anzures et al. (2022) discuss how environmental factors and sustainable practices impact banana production in the Davao Region, reinforcing the idea that effective production methods contribute to overall market success.

Table 13. Mean Distribution of the Participants on the Impact of Post Harvesting Handling and Packaging

Post Harvesting Handling and Packaging	Mean	Interpretation
Branding and packaging of bananas influence consumer perceptions and buying behavior in the market place.	4.33	Agree
There will be no complaining on the part of the consumer if the product is well handled.	4.19	Agree
It will deliver a good quality of bananas in the market place.	4.23	Agree
There will be lesser to no wasted produced banana during the transportation in the market place or the area of distribution.	4.35	Agree
Grand Mean	4.28	Agree

Post-harvest handling and packaging are critical components of the banana marketing chain, as they significantly influence the transition from production to consumer. Table 13 presents the overall interpretation of four parameters related to this determinant, indicating its substantial impact on the banana market chain. Participants agreed that "branding and packaging of bananas influence consumer perceptions and buying behavior," with a mean score of 4.33, reflecting strong agreement. Additionally, most participants concurred that consumers are unlikely to complain if the product is handled properly, as indicated by a mean score of 4.19, also interpreted as agreement. Furthermore, the statement regarding the delivery of high-quality bananas with minimal waste during transportation received mean scores of 4.23 and 4.35, respectively, both interpreted as agreement.

The grand mean score of 4.28 from this table concludes that participants believe post-harvest handling and packaging are among the most important factors influencing the flow of banana marketing in Palimbang. The parameters assessed demonstrate that these practices are effective and essential, aligning with findings presented in Table 8 of this research, which had a grand mean of 3.83 and was similarly interpreted as agreement. This data is supported by Calica et al. (2017), who studied post-harvest handling systems and losses of Cardava bananas in the Philippines, finding that post-harvest losses reached approximately 15.45% due to factors such as dehanding, immature hands, and weight loss. Recent studies further emphasize the significance of post-harvest practices in enhancing banana quality and marketability. For instance, Voora et al. (2023) discuss how effective post-harvest technologies can reduce losses and improve product quality throughout the supply chain. Additionally, research by Anzures et al. (2022) highlights the role of sustainable packaging and handling methods in preserving banana quality during transportation, reinforcing the importance of these practices for consumer satisfaction.

Table 14. Mean Distribution of the Participants on the Impact of Market Access and Distribution

Market Access and Distribution	Mean	Interpretation
The availability of bananas throughout the year affects consumer preferences in the market place.	4.10	Agree
The consumer could easily access the banana within the peripheral of the market place.	4.27	Agree
With the establishment of various market places, it could assure that the banana can be distributed to different areas of distribution.	3.96	Agree
Consumer will be aware of the justified prices of the banana in the market place.	4.07	Agree
The linkages and partnership will shape confidence on the part of the farmers as it will boost the banana supply in the market place.	4.07	Agree
Grand Mean	4.09	Agree

The accessibility of products to the market and their distribution is one of the most crucial aspects of the marketing chain. In Palimbang's banana marketing chain, market access and distribution serve as vital determinants. Table 14 outlines the extent of these determinants based on responses gathered from participants. One notable response related to the year-round availability of bananas, which influences consumer purchasing preferences. This aligns with the findings of Steinhart et al. (2013), who examined how product availability impacts purchase intentions, noting that both positive and negative effects of product availability can significantly influence consumer behavior.

Additionally, other parameters received positive feedback from participants, including statements such as "Consumers can easily access bananas within the market area," "The establishment of various marketplaces ensures banana distribution to different areas,"

"Consumers will be aware of fair prices for bananas," and "Linkages and partnerships will build farmers' confidence and boost banana supply in the market." These statements were interpreted as "Agree," with respective mean scores of 4.27, 3.96, 4.07, and 4.07. Overall, the researcher concluded that these determinants positively affect the banana marketing chain in Palimbang, reflected in a grand mean score of 4.09, which was also interpreted as "Agree." This outcome is supported by recent studies that emphasize the importance of market access and distribution in agricultural supply chains. For example, a study by Boquiren et al. (2023) highlights how effective distribution channels enhance product availability and consumer satisfaction in the banana market. Furthermore, research by Surbakti et al. (2022) discusses the complexities of banana marketing channels in the Philippines, underscoring how improved access and strategic partnerships can lead to better market outcomes for producers.

Table 15. Mean Distribution of the Participants on the Impact of Quality Assurance and Standards

Quality Assurance and Standards	Mean	Interpretation
The quality of bananas significantly influences consumer purchasing decisions in the market place.	4.13	Agree
The income-generated through banana supply and production will increase if the quality and standard of the produced bananas falls within the certification for quality assurance.	4.25	Agree
The demand of banana in the market place will increase if the consumers' is maintained through acceptable standard and quality within the market chain.	4.02	Agree
Grand Mean	4.13	Agree

Quality assurance and standards significantly impact the banana marketing chain, benefiting producers, distributors, retailers, and consumers alike. As a key determinant of this study, the data collected from participant responses indicates that quality assurance ensures consistent banana product quality, safeguards production, enhances market accessibility, improves supply chain efficiency, and ultimately increases consumer satisfaction. Table 15 presents favorable results, with all parameters interpreted as "Agree."

Specifically, the statement "the quality of bananas significantly influences consumer purchasing decisions in the marketplace" received a mean score of 4.13, indicating that most respondents agree that banana quality affects consumer purchasing behavior. Other parameters, such as "Income generated through banana supply and production will increase if the quality and standards of produced bananas meet certification for quality assurance" and "Demand for bananas in the marketplace will rise if acceptable standards and quality are maintained within the market chain," received mean scores of 4.25 and 4.02, respectively. These scores also indicate agreement among participants that established protocols and guidelines are essential to ensure bananas are safe for consumption.

Recent studies further support these findings by highlighting the importance of quality standards in the banana industry. For instance, the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) emphasizes that Good Agricultural Practices (GAP) are crucial for ensuring food safety and quality in banana production (FAO, 2022). Additionally, research by Boquiren et al. (2023) discusses how adherence to quality standards can enhance market access for banana producers while meeting consumer expectations.

Table 16. Mean Distribution of the Participants on the Impact of Marketing Support and Promotion

Marketing Support and Promotion	Mean	Interpretation
Effective marketing and promotion strategies significantly impact the sales of bananas in the market place.	4.29	Agree
Farmers will be more equip in producing good quality banana through various scaffolding of innovation from different sectors.	4.02	Agree
Farmers increases production through financial assistance from various sectors – create meaningful engagement and relationship that enhances the banana production.	3.87	Agree
The increase on demand is visible in the market place.	3.69	Agree
Farmers will have a favorable income through effective support and promotion.	4.08	Agree
Grand Mean	3.99	Agree

The banana marketing chain has experienced significant benefits from marketing support and promotional strategies, which have positively influenced consumer demand, brand perception, production quality, farmer income, and collaboration within the industry. This collective effort has enhanced the overall productivity and profitability of the Palimbang banana sector. According to data derived from participant responses, a majority agreed that effective marketing and promotional strategies significantly boost banana sales in the marketplace. Farmers have become more adept at producing high-quality bananas thanks to various innovative supports from different sectors. Additionally, financial assistance has enabled farmers to increase production while fostering meaningful engagement that enhances banana cultivation. The rise in market demand is evident, and farmers are likely to see improved incomes due to effective support and promotion, reflected in mean scores of 4.29, 4.02, 3.87, 3.69, and 4.08 for various parameters.

The researchers confidently assert that both banana production and harvesting are crucial determinants of the marketing chain in Palimbang. Post-harvest handling and packaging emerge as essential components of this chain. Data indicates that branding and packaging significantly affect consumer perceptions and purchasing behavior, with a mean score of 4.33 indicating agreement among participants. Furthermore, post-harvest handling and packaging are vital for facilitating the flow of bananas in Palimbang, achieving a grand mean of 3.83, also interpreted as "Agree." Accessibility to markets and distribution channels plays a critical role in the banana marketing chain in Palimbang. The findings highlight the importance of ensuring year-round availability of bananas and consumer access within local markets.

Conclusions

The study reveals that marketing constraints significantly impact the profitability and sustainability of banana production in Palimbang. The interconnection between production and marketing is pivotal, as inefficient marketing channels lead to stagnation or decline in farm outputs. This bottleneck affects farmers' incomes and banana prices for consumers, highlighting the need for improved market access and distribution systems. Despite these challenges, farmers across different scales of production demonstrate a high level of knowledge and awareness of the marketing chain. Moreover, those adhering to quality standards are better positioned to secure contracts with exporters, enhancing marketability and profitability. Efficient distribution networks are critical, with shorter supply chains yielding better profitability through reduced transportation costs and handling times. The findings underscore the importance of quality assurance, compliance with market standards, and infrastructure improvements to ensure the sustainability of the banana industry in Palimbang.

To address these challenges, several recommendations are proposed. First, improving local infrastructure, including roads and packing facilities, is essential to facilitate efficient banana distribution and reduce costs. Strengthening cooperative models among farmers can enhance collective bargaining power, resource access, and knowledge sharing, enabling farmers to compete more effectively.

Implementing quality assurance programs and providing training initiatives are also crucial for maintaining standards that align with local and international market demands. Promoting knowledge transfer through partnerships with larger agricultural firms can improve cultivation and post-harvest practices. Moreover, strategies should focus on enhancing market access by connecting farmers directly with consumers and retailers, minimizing intermediaries in the supply chain.

Ongoing research into the banana marketing chain is necessary to identify and address emerging challenges and opportunities. Encouraging sustainable farming practices, such as integrated pest management and organic farming techniques, will further enhance productivity while protecting environmental resources. These measures will significantly improve the efficiency and profitability of the banana marketing chain, benefiting producers, consumers, and the broader economy of Palimbang.

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